

Buying Behaviour of Consumer in Online Shopping

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Abstract: In today's world shopping is the most buzz due to the continuous changes occurring in the purchasing pattern of the consumers in making the shopping. In the recent days like up to decade of 2010 the offline shopping was the most preferred way of doing shopping and availing the services by large number of consumer's. However with the introduction of the Internet, the new generation is proffering mostly the online shopping. The level of easiness available on internet i.e. to say just by clicking the button from the laptop or computer or even mobile anything could be purchased or any service could be availed. Because of these easiness and convenience the more and more consumer is converting into the online consumer. No doubt whatever is the nature of the consumer, whether offline or online, he is always, each one is a potential consumer for the company. Due to continuous and rapid development of technology, and growth of internet, every company has to find out the new consumer's even though the consumer is making purchase online or using any mode. The reason of this is to face the cut throat competition existing in the market. Since market have so many potential consumers having varied nature of demands, hence it becomes most important for companies to understand what they actually want.

Keywords; Online Shopping, Consumer, Behaviour, Technology, Competition, Convenience.

INTRODUCTION

For making this exercise it is of vital importance to understand and analyze as well to identify the factor that impacts or influences the consumer's choice and factors which he considers while making the shopping, whether online or offline. In Indian context it becomes more important because, Indian consumers still prefer the offline shopping and concentrates on online shopping. Hence for manufacturer's it is of quite importance to understand what actually impacts the buying behaviour of consumer's in both the markets i.e. in online as well as in offline. As we said earlier, that various researches have been conducted to analyse the buying behaviour of consumer's especially in the area of Online shopping, but since the online shopping craze is not old in India, and quite new, and hence it becomes very difficult to analyze the behaviour of online consumer's compare to analyze the behaviour of traditional consumer. If a buyer wants to make shopping online, it becomes quite important to know what the factors which influence their purchases are? These factor's help to know the retailer, manufacturers and dealers to what a consumer wants and helps to satisfy the consumer's need. With using this background, the researcher is finding out the main factors

which could influence the decision of online consumer while making the purchase, along with the risk involved in making consumer satisfied. The results of above study will definitely help out the consumers to improve their look out and perception towards making shopping online.

REVIEW OF LITREATURE

Bhatnagar, Misra, and Rao (2000), in their recent study made a shot to review the danger, convenience and Internet shopping behaviour. They found that legal status has no effect on purchase behaviour and located mixed results based upon gender (except for specific gender-related products), years on the web, and age.

Caudill and Murphy (2000) opined that consumer privacy was a public policy issue that had received considerable attention over the last thirty years. the exceptional growth of the net had spawned new concerns about protecting the privacy of consumers. It observed both historical and conceptual analyses of privacy and discussed domestic and international regulatory and self-regulatory approaches to challenging privacy issues on the net. It also reviewed ethical theories that apply to consumer privacy and offered specific suggestions for corporate ethical policy and public policy furthermore as a hunt agenda.

Chowdhury and Rahman (2015) focussed that web shoppers are variety loves, but at the identical time, they're also cautious on the worth and time that they spent. Maximum respondent relies on price and their experience because the basis of the standard judgment of things in online shopping. However, the foremost significant disadvantage of online shopping, as indicated by the study is that products can not be touched or trialled at the time of purchase. As far as payment options are concerned, online shopping offers several payment options like cash on delivery or payment through internet banking or payment by charge account credit or MasterCard, and so on. However, most of the buyers preferred cash on delivery.

Gopal and Jindoliya (2016) have focused that earlier few years have seen unprecedented growth within the number of online business players. This ever-increasing competition has necessitated the adoption of innovative marketing strategies, new media and 'out of box thinking' to affect the customer to go to the positioning and make purchases. In India, e-tailing has the potential to grow over hundred-fold to succeed in a worth of \$76 billion by 2021. The country's growing internet-habituated consumer base, which is able to form about 180 million broadband users by 2020, together with a burgeoning class of mobile Internet users, drive the net shopping store.

Jayakumar & Kumar (2013) focused on the attitude of consumer towards internet shopping in Chennai city of Tamil Nadu. The information was collected form 100 respondents through sampling. A questionnaire survey method was accustomed measure the attitude of internet shopping. The result revealed that attitude of consumer towards internet shopping was positively and significantly associated with age, gender and monthly income. However, it absolutely was negatively associated with educational qualification, size of family and nature of family. Hence, the results proved that consumers' behaviour significantly differs while shopping online.

Kuppuraj and Ravichandran (2014) aimed to analyse one in every of the fastest growing areas of e-commerce is online purchasing, the web provides a platform where sellers and buyers can are available in contact for the sale and get of products and services. The physical goods are revealed in e-store websites and delivered on to the house. Online consumers are fresh and educated graduates in order that they could easily access the web reception for purchase transactions on the specified time and any month. They feel it's cheaper and easy to buy by cash payment options.

OBJECTIVE OF STUDY

This is well understood that a research is supposed to have a definite value addition to existing literature available on that Subject Matter. Without this the objective of the research is not fulfilled and efforts made in research are not useful. In the same way this research also provides a value addition literature to the existing literature available on “Consumer’s Buying Behaviour toward online shopping. The study is directed to explore the factors which could impact the buyer’s behaviour towards online shopping and that is required because in today’s business world consumer’s behaviour is the most important factor for success of any business. This research has been directed to provide suggestions, which definitely will help in retention of the consumers of online traders. Followings are some of the objectives of carrying out this research

- Finding out the factors which could influence the buying behavior of online consumer.
- Finding out the preference of consumers in relation of Goods and Services for online purchase
- Finding out the preference of consumer according to their age in online shipping.
- To make a study of relationship between demographical factors and consumer buying behaviour towards online shopping.
- To Identify problems of online shopping online

HYPOTHESIS FOR STUDY

Null Hypothesis (H₀) : There is no significant difference of purchase intention among the offline and online consumers.

Null Hypothesis (H₀) : There is no Significant difference in decision regarding Online shopping and Offline Shopping.

ONLINE SHOPPING

Internet no doubt, made life of everyone easy and convenient. The business not at all exception to this. It has changed not completely but yes to a great extent, the way of doing business, and business in India has made their presence worldwide through E-Commerce or online shopping. Online shopping is a medium where goods and services are sold and purchased through internet. This is now co-operating a larger portion of total GDP of the country as high income generating activity. This is not only for Indian Business, but business of other countries are also showing their presence in India. The entire world market is now like small village and distance is not at all a constraint. At the beginning of the E-Commerce only those sellers was selling their product online who was not having any establishment of their shops, but now even those who has their set up of business shops are also on E-Commerce portals and online Shopping websites, and perhaps they are earning better from Online than offline. The virtual world is overruling out the physical market due to availability of variety of products and services. One important thing is that earlier (i.e. Before introduction of E-Commerce) customer has to approach to seller. Sometime it happens that consumer though of any product of his need but due to lack of market he was in perception that this kind of product actually do not exist or otherwise he was not aware where this product could be available. Now he just needs to think about this and search the product on internet and he can that product and can know about the place where such product could be available. Even companies or sellers approach to consumer for sale of their product. The India’s leaders of online shopping are Flipcart.com, Snap deal.com, Paytm. Com. Homeshop18.com, Futurebazaar.com, Firstcry.com and many others. Now the big sized corporates has also entered into E-Commerce business like Tata (Tata Cliq) and Reliance, Adani group etc. Neilson Global Consumer Report, (2010), the growth of online shopping is not the result of only huge or large size players in the market, but also because of rapid growth of various online retailers who have their online portals and E-Stores which sale a variety of products to their customers. E-Tailing which compare to E-Commerce is a new term but is actually a part of E-Commerce. E-Tailing is a replacement of retailing in E-Commerce. It is retailing conducted online mode using the internet, where goods and services are sold to consumers on internet. Various Services of E-Store or online Services includes Delivery of product on right time, Easy return and replacement process, timely

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response to consumer and their complaints. Using internet the consumers collect varied nature of information about the desired product and can compare it with other available product of low price and of same quality. Online business or E-Commerce Business offers increased activities for retailers by the way of access to growing and enlarged market, along with decreased operating cost as well as low cost of purchase. With use of E-Tailers, consumer is becoming more smart and making buying or shopping as per their convenience. As we discussed earlier there are number of factors that makes online shopping more attractive and unique and different from offline shopping. Besides having convenience and comfort, online shopping also allows to customer to access and compare the information of product from multiple sources.

SCOPE OF THE STUDY

The Above study is targeted towards Behaviour of consumers towards online shopping. As we can see that users of internet is increasing day by day. People are more devotedly using the Technology, hence craze for online shopping has also increased drastically. This study is mainly carried out to find out what people use to think or have perception towards Online Shopping and how they accordingly behave in their buying Behaviour while making online shopping. This attitude or behaviour of consumer is, perhaps the most vital factor that effect's the sales in online market. Although it is difficult to assess the exact behaviour of consumer in online shopping, and as such a very little information is available on consumer buying behaviour in online shopping, hence it becomes very important to understand the behaviour of consumer in internet shopping and factors which impacts behaviour of consumer in online shopping decisions. We will analyse the purchase intentions and will try to find out why people do or do not make shopping online. There are various factors which perhaps impacts the Consumer behaviour for shopping online includes Security in online shopping, Quality of the product, nature of the supplier, trusted website and loss of data related to personal information.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Source of DATA

Primary data will be collected through well-structured questionnaire. The questionnaire is being developed with the help of literature review and consultation. Data will be collected from the shopping malls. Consumers will be contacted through personally and through e-mail also. Secondary data will be used from the previous studies, internet, magazines, journals etc.

Sampling Technique

The sampling method that was considered appropriate for this study was convenient sampling. The full sample as mentioned below is once again divided based on the different possible benefits available to consumer in online and offline shopping.

Sampling Design

Our study, on is mainly carried out through Questionnaire mode, which is Primary used for data collection. Self administered close ended questionnaire was prepared because it is found to be more efficient and standardized comparing to open ended questionnaire. It is also found to be more appropriate in securing factual information.

RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

Table No. 1 is concerned with various parameters related to level of preference of the consumers in online and offline shopping.

Table: 1

Presentation of Data for Selection, and Recruitment along with Nature of Work							
S. No.	Question asked in Questionnaire	Yes		No		Total	
		F	%	F	%	F	%
1	Are you impacted by the discounts given by Online websites?	440	88%	60	12%	500	100%
2	Are you satisfied with the quality of Product delivered?	475	95%	25	5%	500	100%
3	Return policy is satisfactory or not?	395	79%	105	21%	500	100%
4	Online shopping gives you the comfort of the home shopping?	500	100%	0	0%	500	100%
5	Online shopping gives you better options then offline shopping?	400	80%	100	20%	500	100%
6	Online shopping Gives you facility of comparison of the product of the different companies?	410	82%	90	18%	500	100%

CHART 1

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The online shopping platform gives customer friendly ecosystem, provide funny and new due to discover product and services. All the more, it offers great discount and rewards. Various online shopping websites offer cash-back, discounts and rebates. Once we visit a store offline, we are likely to obtain the value merchant has placed on specific product. This is often not the case with shopping online; there we've the aptitude to assess prices from various vendors. Shelf area in offline store is incredibly limited, that indicates type of product is prescribed while in online shopping there's no constraint on shelf space. It's also very simple to test reviews of other customers before making purchase decision in online shopping. For improving customer experience and online purchases, it's concluded that security parameter

in online shopping is extremely essential and most significant as compared to other parameters. However, there are several other parameters that influence online shopping. The protection can be in terms of payment or giving personal information as people are really concerned about security measures adopted by website before making purchase decision. Online shopping isn't complex. As many efforts are made to form online shopping more simple. High resolution images, videos, reviews are making it more easy for customer to decide on and compare products. We are able to also access all product parameters and price to determine which product has higher worth. Customer care helpline are available 24 x 7 which clarifies if customer has any doubt regarding online purchase. Returns also are made easier by online shopping website with none questions asked, except in cases where product is employed or its perishable product. Some clothing websites even give 1 month time to exchange or return the item. And also we get all products delivered and picked up for return from home, so customers needn't to stress about time period, long queue or traffic jams.

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